

Theoretical Predictions of the Strength Behavior of Short-Fiber Reinforced Metals

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ABSTRACT

This paper examines the effects of fiber geometrical arrangements as well as plastic deformation of matrix material on the strength of short fiber composites. Local stress concentrations in the elastic and ideally plastic matrix material with random distribution of unidirectional short fibers have been determined. The size of fiber-end-gaps has been estimated by a probabilistic approach. Theoretical predictions of composite strength have been performed and the results are expressed as functions of material properties, total number of fibers and a critical zone parameter.

INTRODUCTION

Discontinuous fiber reinforced metal matrix composites are gaining increasing technological importance due to their versatility in properties and high performance. Unlike continuous fiber composites the mechanical behavior of short fiber composites is often dominated by the complex stress distributions due to fiber discontinuities (1,2,3). The local stress concentration at fiber ends in particular plays a critical role in affecting the performance of short fiber composites, and it often reduces the strength of a short fiber composite to a level far less than that of a continuous fiber composite with the same fiber volume content. Several theories (1) have been proposed to predict the strength of short fiber composites. One type of theory is based on the modification of the "rule of mixtures," which was originally developed for continuous fiber composites. Since the axial stress distribution in a short fiber is not uniform, the rule of mixtures has been modified by researchers to take into account the effect of fibers length.

The present paper treats the case of aligned short fiber composites. The discontinuity of fibers gives rise to gaps between adjacent fiber ends. The collection of the adjacent fiber ends is termed a "fiber-end-gap" (see Fig. 1). The width of a fiber-end-gap depends upon the number of fiber ends in the gap. The existence of a fiber-end-gap inevitably induces a stress concentration on the fibers bridging such a gap. Thus the fracture of a bridging fiber can take place at locations of high stress concentration while the stress level in most parts of the fiber is well below the ultimate strength. Such a failure mechanism needs to be taken into account in the modification of the rule of mixtures.

Bader, Chou and Quigley (4) first proposed the concept of a critical zone in dealing with short fiber composite strength and defined the fibers in the zone as either ending fibers or bridging fibers. Since the distribution of fibers is normally fairly random, it is natural to examine the strength of short fiber composites by a probabilistic method. This approach was adopted by Fukuda and Chou (5). In this paper, the concepts of Bader, Chou and Quigley (4) and Fukuda and Chou (5) are expanded to a more general strength model taking into account the size effect. Furthermore, the matrix material is allowed to deform elastically as well as elastically and perfect-plastically.

STRENGTH THEORY

General Formulation

It is assumed that the fibers are sufficiently long and failure of the composite occurs due to fiber breakage by local stress concentrations. Figure 1 shows the schematic representation of the effect of fiber configuration on the composite strength. Two typical examples of fiber configuration are considered. Case (a) obviously gives rise to comparatively larger stress concentrations on the bridging fiber at the location marked x than case (b). For very large numbers of fibers in a composite, it can be assumed that the mean stress of composite is the same in both cases (a) and (b) under the same applied strain. However, due to the large local stress concentration in case (a), the stress at point x reaches the fiber's ultimate strength at the strain level much lower than that of case (b).

The formulation of the composite strength prediction is performed in three stages:

- (1) Derivation of the probability of finding fiber-end-gaps of different sizes.
- (2) Determination of the stress concentration factor for each fiber-end-gap configuration.
- (3) Determination of the mean stress in composite at the failure of short fibers due to local stress concentrations.

Probabilistic Approach to Determine Fiber-End-Gap Size

The fiber-end-gap is modelled for the case of two-dimensional array shown in Fig. 1. The size of the critical zone (4) is denoted by $\beta\ell$, where ℓ is average fiber length and $0 < \beta < 1$. Focussing the attention on a single fiber end, the probability that this fiber end is in the gap consisting of n fiber ends, P_n , is

$$P_n = n\beta^{n-1}(1-\beta)^2 \quad (1)$$

and

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} P_n = 1. \quad (2)$$

The probability that a given fiber end is not in any one of the gaps with more than n fiber ends is

$$Q_n = 1 - \sum_{i=n+1}^{\infty} P_i. \quad (3)$$

When the above probability is independent for each fiber, the probability that there is no gap larger than size n is

$$\tilde{P}(n) = (Q_n)^N \quad (4)$$

where N is the total number of fibers in a plane transverse to the fiber direction. However, actually Q_n for a given fiber is not independent of the other fibers. When N is sufficiently larger than the average gap size \bar{n} , it is more suitable to express $\tilde{P}(n)$ of Eq. (4) as

$$\tilde{P}(n) = (Q_n)^{N/\bar{n}} \quad (5)$$

where

$$\bar{n} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n P_n \quad (6)$$

Using Eqs. (1), (3), and (6), Eq. (5) can be rewritten as

$$\tilde{P}(n) = [1 - \beta^{n-1}((n-1)(1-\beta)+1)]^{N\beta'} \quad (7)$$

and

$$\beta' = \frac{1}{\bar{n}} = \frac{1-\beta}{1+\beta} \quad (8)$$

$\tilde{P}(n)$ can be used to determine the strength of short fiber composites through the relation between gap size n and stress concentration. Figure 2 demonstrates the variation of $\tilde{P}(n)$ with N and β . It can be shown that $\tilde{P}(n)$ behaves like step function and $\tilde{P}(n)$ changes from 0 to 1 at $n = M$ where M is determined from

$$\beta^{n-1}[(n-1)(1-\beta)+1]^{N\beta'} = 1 \quad (9)$$

M obtained from Eq. (9) is termed the "most probable gap size." For $N \rightarrow \infty$, the asymptotic form of the cumulative probability distribution function of $\tilde{P}(n)$ can be readily derived. Figure 3 shows M as a function of β and N . For actual composites, the values of M do not vary tremendously with β and N .

Local Stress Concentration

The stress concentration due to a fiber-end-gap is estimated for the case where the matrix is elastic and ideally plastic. It is assumed that the fiber length is much larger than the critical length and hence the case of long fibers only is considered for evaluating stress concentration.

Hedgepeth (6,7) pioneered the study of stress concentration in continuous fiber composites based upon the shear lag analysis. He obtained closed form solutions of the stress concentration factor for the elastic case and showed a numerical example for the elastic and ideally plastic material case with one broken fiber. Following the method of influence function and the assumptions of shear lag analysis, the stress concentration factor for an arbitrary fiber-end-gap size within the limit of small scale yielding condition has been examined.

The model of composite is shown in Fig. 4. There are $2a+1$ broken fibers and they are denoted as $n = -a, -a+1, \dots, a-1$ and a . The surrounding unbroken fibers are denoted as $\pm(a+1), \pm(a+2), \dots$, etc. As the applied loading increases, the shear stress of the matrix first increases elastically to a shear strength τ_y , after which plastic deformation occurs at the tip of the fiber-end-gap between the broken fibers, $n = \pm a$, and the adjacent bridging fibers, $n = \pm(a+1)$, and the shear stress remains constant. The extent of plastic deformation in the fiber direction is denoted by α .

The mathematical analysis of the stress concentration is rather complicated. For the case of small scale plastic deformation, the stress concentration factor can be expressed in the following simple form

$$K = K_0 \left(1 - \frac{2a+1}{4a+3} \cdot \frac{\alpha^2}{2} \right) \quad (10)$$

where

$$\alpha = \frac{\pi(a+1)(2a+1)}{K_0^2(4a+3)} - \frac{1}{K_0} \frac{1}{q} \quad (11)$$

$$q = \frac{P}{\tau_y} \left(\frac{G}{dEAh} \right)^{1/2} \quad (12)$$

and

$$K_0 = \frac{4 \cdot 6 \cdot 8 \dots (4a+4)}{3 \cdot 5 \cdot 7 \dots (4a+3)} \quad (13)$$

Here, K_0 is the stress intensity factor for the elastic case (6,7). P is the applied load in the fiber at infinity. A is fiber cross-sectional area, d is fiber spacing, h is the thickness of matrix material between two neighboring fibers, E is fiber elastic modulus, and G is matrix shear modulus. Figure 5 indicates that K is first constant and then it decreases with increasing applied stress. The arrows indicate the on-set of plastic deformation. The critical stress for plastic deformation to take place has been obtained in close form solutions. Figure 6 shows α as a function of the dimensionless applied stress q .

Strength of Composite Material

Assuming uniform fiber strength, the rule of mixtures can be modified as

$$\sigma_{cu} = V_f \frac{\sigma_{fu}}{K_M} + (1-V_f)\sigma'_m \quad (14)$$

where σ_{cu} and σ_{fu} denote, respectively, composite and fiber ultimate strength, V_f is fiber volume fraction, σ'_m is the stress of the matrix at the failure of the composite, and K_M is the stress concentration factor for the fiber-end-gap of size M .

The mean value of composite strength is defined as

$$\sigma_{cu}^{mean} = \int \sigma_{cu} R(\sigma_{cu}) d\sigma_{cu} \quad (15)$$

where

$$R(\sigma_{cu}) = \frac{d\bar{P}(M)}{dM} \frac{dM}{d\sigma_{cu}} \quad (16)$$

By approximating $\bar{P}(M)$ as a step function and determining M from Eq. (9), σ_{cu}^{mean} can be evaluated. The results of the analysis can demonstrate a size effect on composite strength.

Numerical Results

Figure 7 shows the results of calculations of composite strength as a function of fiber volume fraction V_f without considering the effect of plasticity. In this calculation, we adopted the values of $\lambda = 0.5$ mm, $\lambda_c = 0.1$ mm, $d = 0.01$ mm and $\beta = 0.2$, which were used by Fukuda and Chou (5). As expected, the slope of the line is affected by the total number of fibers N , and it decreases monotonously with increasing N . This indicates the size effect on the strength of the composite in the case of elastic matrix.

When the shear strength of the matrix is low, the strength of the composite is less affected by the stress concentration of the fiber-end-gap. Figure 8 shows the increase of slope $d\sigma_{cu}/dV_f$ with the decrease of shear strength of matrix, τ_y . Although calculations have been yet performed only for the case of small plastic deformation, it is expected that the slope $d\sigma_{cu}/dV_f$ approaches σ_{fu} as τ_y goes to 0.

CONCLUSIONS

A theoretical study has been conducted to predict the effect of stress concentrations caused by fiber-end-gaps on the strength of unidirectional short fiber composites, with elastic or elastic and ideally plastic matrix. By a

probabilistic approach, the magnitude of the most probable maximum size of fiber-end-gap has been calculated as a function of the total number of fibers and a critical zone parameter. Then the stress concentration factor at the tip of the fiber-end-gap is estimated under the assumption of small scale plastic deformation. The present study has shown that the size effect on composite strength is moderate for composites with an elastic matrix, and the size effect is reduced by plastic deformation at the tip of the gap.

The calculation of stress concentration factor for large plastic deformation also has been performed. However, due to the limitations in space, it will be reported in a future publication.

REFERENCES

1. Chou, T. W., and Kelly, A., *Mater. Sci. Eng.*, 25 (1976), 35.
2. Idem, *Ann. Rev. Mater. Sci.*, 10 (1980), 229.
3. Vinson, J. R., and Chou, T. W., Composite Materials and Their Use in Structures, Elsevier-Applied Science, London, 1975.
4. Bader, M. G., Chou, T. W., and Quigley, J., in "New Developments and Applications in Composites" edited by Wilsdorf, The Metallurgical Society-American Institute of Mining Metallurgy and Petroleum Engineering, New York, 1979.
5. Fukuda, H., and Chou, T. W., *J. Mater. Sci.*, 16 (1981), 1088.
6. Hedgepeth, J. M., NASA TND-882 (1961).
7. Hedgepeth, J. M., and Van Dyke, J. *Compos. Mater.*, 1 (1967), 294.
8. Fichter, W. B., NASA TN-5453 (1969).

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Fig.1 Schematic representation of fiber configuration. A typical site of stress concentration is indicated by x in (a).

Fig.2 Cumulative probability distribution function

Fig.3 Most probable maximum gap size, M vs. critical zone parameter, β . N denotes the total number of fibers.

Fig.4 Plastic deformation at the tip of a fiber-end-gap

Fig.5 Stress concentration factor K vs. non-dimensional load q . The numbers of broken fibers are indicated.

Fig.6 Plastic deformation zone, α vs. nondimensional applied load, q . The number of fractured fibers are indicated in the curves.

Fig.7 Composite strength as the function of fiber volume fraction

Fig.8 Effect of matrix ductility on the strength of composite.